
Seminar on Water Quality Management Trade-Offs

Point Source vs. Diffuse Source Pollution

(Conference)
September 16-17, 1980
Chicago, Illinois

FOREWARD

The Environmental Protection Agency was established to coordinate administration of the major Federal programs designed to protect the quality of our environment.

An important part of the Agency's effort involves the search for information about environmental problems, management techniques, and new technologies through which optimum use of the nation's land and water resources can be assured and the threat pollution poses to the welfare of the American people can be minimized.

The report contributes to the knowledge essential if the United States Environmental Protection Agency is to meet the requirements of environmental laws that it establish and enforce pollution control standards which are reasonable, cost-effective and provide adequate protection for the American public.

The Great Lakes National Program Office (GLNPO) of the United States Environmental Protection Agency, was established in Region V, Chicago to provide a specific focus on the water quality concerns of the Great Lakes. GLNPO provides funding for Great Lakes demonstration grants under Section 108(a) as well as provides personnel support to the International Joint Commission activities under the U.S.-Canada Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement.

Several land use water quality studies have been funded to support the Pollution from Land Use Activities Reference Group (PLUARG) under the Agreement to address specific objectives related to land use pollution to the Great Lakes. This report describes a methodology for integrating point and diffuse source control practices and costs in both large and small watersheds.

The conference committee consisted of Ralph G. Christensen, Section 108(a) Coordinator; Carl D. Wilson, Regional Nonpoint Source Coordinator; Clifford Risley, Regional Research and Development Representative; Don Urban, USDA - Soil Conservation Service; and Orville Macomber, Center for Environmental Research Information.

We hope that the information and data contained herein will help planners and managers of pollution control agencies make better decisions for carrying forward their pollution control responsibilities.

Madonna F. McGrath
Director
Great Lakes National Program Office

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SEMINAR ON WATER QUALITY MANAGEMENT TRADE-OFFS
(Point Source vs. Diffuse Source Pollution)

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UPSTREAM POINT SOURCE PHOSPHORUS INPUTS AND EFFECTS

by

David B. Baker*

One of the goals of water quality management is to obtain the greatest possible improvement in water quality and general environmental quality per dollar invested in pollution abatement programs. Although most water quality management plans include an economic analysis of alternative solutions to some particular problem, very often the examination of alternatives operates within a very narrow segment of the overall interacting set of causes and effects determining water quality. For example, a facility plan might include the selection of the most cost effective method of reducing the phosphorus concentrations in an effluent from 3 mg/l to 1 mg/l. If this reduction has no effect on water quality or if comparable expenditures on nonpoint controls or flow augmentation would have greater water quality benefits, then the examination of alternatives has operated within too narrow a framework of options. Certainly the objectives of this symposium and the concepts incorporated into the Watershed Model reflect the need to broaden the perspectives within which alternatives can be evaluated.

Although the concept of integrated point/nonpoint control programs is clear, the development and implementation of such programs is difficult because adequate data and necessary understanding is generally not available. In planning an integrated control program in the Great Lakes, the relationships outlined in the model illustrated in Figure 1 should be understood. The quality, quantity, timing and variability of inputs from both point and nonpoint sources into each area of the aquatic system should be known. Knowledge of the physical, chemical or biological processing of inputs within each area is important. This processing both affects and is affected by the water quality in the area. The processing also affects the movement of materials into either temporary or permanent storage within the system and the output of materials to the next area downstream. As the number of steps between a particular input and a water quality effect increases the more tenuous the cause and effect relationships become. This is certainly the case for the relationships between point source phosphorus inputs to stream systems and open lake water quality in Lake Erie.

Because of the complexities of the interacting systems illustrated in Figure 1, current efforts at integrated point/nonpoint control programs involve the use of a number of simplifying assumptions. Although the use of such assumptions does allow the development of integrated control programs, their use may undercut the effectiveness of the programs and prevent the realization of control economies that, given more information and better understanding, could be achieved.

The management of phosphorus within the Lake Erie Basin is one area in which opportunities for integrated point/nonpoint source management exist. Some of the major assumptions upon which such programs are based

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Figure 1. Areas requiring data and understanding to support the development of effective and economical integrated point source/nonpoint source control programs in the Lake Erie Basin. Abbreviations: PS, point sources; NPS, nonpoint sources; W.Q., water quality.

include:

1. Upstream (indirect) point source phosphorus inputs are assumed to have 100% delivery through the river to the lake unless large lakes or reservoirs are situated on the river system.
2. The bioavailability of upstream point source phosphorus is assumed to remain constant during transport to the lake.
3. Reductions in sediment and particulate phosphorus yields at river mouths are assumed to be proportional to the reduction in gross erosion achieved by the application of best management practices in the watershed.
4. No systematic differences in the processing of point source and nonpoint source-derived phosphorus within the estuaries and near shore zones of the lake are assumed to occur even though the mode of delivery of phosphorus derived from the two sources is very different.

In this paper some of the assumptions regarding the effects of upstream point source phosphorus inputs will be examined using data available in the Sandusky River Basin. The data indicates that most of the phosphorus entering the river from upstream point sources becomes tied up within the river bottom sediments. Its eventual delivery to the lake is in the form of particulate rather than soluble phosphorus. The delivery ratio of this phosphorus to the lake is probably less than 100%. Evidence of ambient stream water quality problems associated with point source phosphorus loading is lacking. The nonpoint source phosphorus loading component is so large and variable that the effects of further point source control programs in reducing phosphorus output from the basin could not be directly measured. The transfer of funds from portions of phosphorus removal programs at upstream municipalities to alternate uses such as flow augmentation or nonpoint controls should be examined.

Upstream Point Source Phosphorus Inputs in the Sandusky Basin

There are seven municipal sewage treatment plants located in the Sandusky River Basin upstream from the Tindall Bridge gaging station near Fremont, Ohio. These plants are identified in Table 1 and their flows, effluent phosphorus concentrations, loading rates and annual loads are listed. Three of the plants have flows greater than 1 MGD and consequently are required to meet a 1 mg/l phosphorus effluent standard. Of these three plants, Bucyrus has no phosphorus removal program; Upper Sandusky has a partial phosphorus removal program and Tiffin has a removal program which meets current requirements. No phosphorus removal programs are in effect at the other sewage treatment plants. The locations of these plants are shown in Figure 2 which also includes the locations of the nutrient and sediment transport stations in the Sandusky Basin.

The combined effluents of these plants load phosphorus into the river system at an average rate of 5.3 kg/hr. The annual loading from

Figure 2. Location of Municipal Sewage Treatment Plants and Sediment and Nutrient Transport Stations in the Sandusky River Basin

the plants is about 45 metric tons per year. The mean annual export of total phosphorus at the Fremont gaging station is 355 metric tons per year (Baker, 1980). Assuming that all of the upstream municipally derived phosphorus is exported from the basin, point sources account for 13 percent of the total load and nonpoint sources 87 percent.

Table 1. Indirect Municipal Point Source Phosphorus Discharges in the Sandusky River Basin, 1978

Location	10 ³ M ³ Flow /day (MGD)	Total Phos. mg/l	Loading Rate Kg/hr.	Annual Load M Ton/yr.
Crestline	2.1 (.55)	6 ^a	.52	4.6
Bucyrus	7.7 (1.9)	8.0	2.6	22
Upper Sandusky	6.4 (1.7)	2.5	.67	5.8
Cary	2.3 (.6)	6 ^a	.57	5.0
Attica	.87 (.23)	6 ^a	.22	1.9
Bloomville	1.1 (.28)	4 ^a	.18	1.6
Tiffin	13. (3.5)	0.9	.49	4.3
Total	33 (8.8)		5.3	45

a Estimated. Data from IJC 1979; De Pinto, et al, 1980, and Ohio EPA, 1979.

Instream Deposition of Phosphorus from Municipal Point Sources

The extent of deposition of municipally derived phosphorus in the Sandusky Basin can be studied through an analysis of both flux patterns and concentration patterns. Since the transport stations in the Sandusky Basin have been operated on a continuous basis for periods from 3 to 5 years, extensive data is available on phosphorus transport rates during both low and high flows. These data can be arranged in the form of flux exceedency tables. A summary of the phosphorus flux exceedency table for the Fremont gaging station is shown in Table 2.

The data in Table 2 are based on the analysis of 2,304 samples collected between December 26, 1973 and November 30, 1979. These samples were used to characterize the stream transport for a total period of 32,635 hours (3.73 years) with individual sample characterizing transport for periods ranging from 3 to 24 hours. During this time a total of 2,097 metric tons of total phosphorus and 393 metric tons of soluble reactive phosphorus were exported past the station. A computer program is used to rank all of the samples on the basis of instantaneous flux from the lowest to the highest value. The program lists the individual flux, the percent of the total period of time the fluxes were equal to or less than the listed value and the percent of the total flux accounted for by the listed value and all smaller flux rates. For example, 70% of the time the flux rate of total phosphorus was 16.5 kg/hr. or less and during that time 4.0% of the total observed total phosphorus flux had been exported.

The weighted average stream flow during the period of observation was 39 m³/sec. This compares with a long term average discharge at the

Fremont station of 27 m³/sec. Thus the data set is biased toward high flows.

Table 2. Characteristics of Phosphorus Export from the Sandusky River Basin, Tindall Bridge, Fremont, Ohio, 1974-1979

Time Weighted Percentile (instantaneous Flux)	Total Phosphorus		Soluble Reactive Phosphorus	
	Flux Rate Kg/hr.	Cum. % of Annual Load	Flux Rate Kg/hr.	Cum. % of Annual Load
10	.74	.08	.16	.07
20	1.33	.24	.37	.27
30	2.08	.50	.70	.70
40	3.06	.89	1.13	1.4
50	4.32	1.5	1.89	2.6
60	7.03	2.3	3.06	4.6
70	16.5	4.0	5.44	7.9
80	41.3	8.2	11.7	14.
90	137	20.	33.6	32
95	339	37	61.2	49
98	776	61	112	69
100	2610	100	587	100

From Table 2 it is apparent that the combined export of phosphorus from all sources is less than the point source inputs for more than 50% of the time. Fifty percent of the time the flux rate of total phosphorus at the Fremont station was less than 4.32 kg/hr.

It should also be noted that when the flux rate is 4.32 kg/hr. only about one third of that phosphorus could have come from point source inputs. Since the flux increases with stream discharge, the median flux should correspond to the median stream discharge. At the Fremont stream gage the median discharge rate is 563 X 10³ M³/day. The combined flow of the upstream municipal sewage treatment plants is 33 X 10³ M³/day. Therefore, 530 X 10³ M³/day or 94% of the median stream flow, is derived from various components of the basin hydrological cycle. In Sandusky subbasins lacking point source phosphorus inputs (Tymochtee Creek, Broken Sword and Wolf, East), the average phosphorus concentration at the median flow is 0.13 to 0.14 mg/l. Assuming that these are the background concentration characteristics of the Sandusky Basin at median stream flows, the background phosphorus flux at the Fremont gage would be 2.9 kg/hr. Consequently, of the 4.3 kg/hr. median flux, only 1.4 kg/hr. could be derived from point source inputs. This is about 25% of the point source input rate of 5.3 kg/hr. These calculations are summarized in Table 3.

The data presented in Table 2 also show that only 1.5% of the total observed load had been exported by the cumulative fluxes lower than the median flux. Applying this figure to the average annual export of phosphorus at the Fremont gage, suggests that only 5.3 metric tons of phosphorus would have been exported during the 50% of the time with the lowest fluxes. Since the loading rate from municipal sources is rather constant, one half of the annual point source inputs of phosphorus

(22.5 metric tons) would have entered the river during this time. Thus during this time the combined point and nonpoint phosphorus export is only 24% of the point source phosphorus inputs. Since much of the phosphorus export during this time is derived from nonpoint sources, it is evident that the bulk of the point source phosphorus inputs is being incorporated into the stream sediments.

Table 3. Components of the Median Phosphorus Flux at Tindall Bridge in Fremont

Median Stream Discharge	563 x 10 ³ M ³ /day
Combined STP Discharges	-33 x 10 ³ M ³ /day
Background Stream Flow	530 x 10 ³ M ³ /day
Background Phosphorus Conc.	0.133 mg/l
Background Phosphorus Flux	2.9 Kg/hr.
Median Phosphorus Flux	4.3 Kg/hr.
Point Source Component of Flux	1.4 Kg/hr.
Point Source Input Rate	5.3 Kg/hr.

The occurrence of instream deposition of phosphorus from municipal point sources is also apparent from studies of the patterns of phosphorus concentration along the river. During the summer of 1974, from 32 to 52 samples were collected during nonstorm conditions at each of twenty six stations along the mainstream of the Sandusky River. The mean concentrations of total and soluble reactive phosphorus are shown as a function of mile point (distance from the river mouth) in Figure 3. The effects of inputs from the Bucyrus, Upper Sandusky and Tiffin sewage treatment plants are evident. None of the plants had phosphorus removal programs in operation at that time. The decreases in phosphorus concentration below each town reflect deposition of phosphorus rather than dilution effects. These data have been presented and discussed in the Proceedings of the Sandusky River Basin Symposium (Baker and Kramer, 1975).

Figure 3. Profiles of mean concentrations of phosphorus along the river system during June through September, 1974. Mileages shown are the distances from the mouth of the river. The three peaks in phosphorus concentration are caused by the effluents of the Bucyrus, Upper Sandusky and Tiffin sewage treatment plants.

Export of Upstream Point Source Phosphorus Inputs

Transmission Coefficients: Although it is evident from the above discussion that much of the upstream point source phosphorus input is incorporated into the river sediments, it is generally assumed that this phosphorus is resuspended during high flow periods and subsequently transported as available phosphorus to Lake Erie (Sonzogni, et al, 1980). Considerable evidence has been accumulated which documents the significance of deposition-resuspension phenomena in the transport of both sediments and phosphorus through river systems (Verhoff, et al, 1978; U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, 1979). Although mass balances for individual storms moving through the Sandusky Basin have been conducted (Melfi & Verhoff, 1979) the results do not provide information on the transmission coefficient of point source-derived phosphorus through the stream system on an annual basis.

One approach to determining the transmission coefficient from upstream point source inputs would be to achieve a known reduction in phosphorus inputs from these sources and compare this with an accompanying reduction in total river export of phosphorus. This approach does not work well where point source inputs are small relative to nonpoint inputs and where nonpoint inputs are extremely variable from year to year. From a study in 1972 (Baker and Kramer, 1973) the mean annual export of total phosphorus from the Sandusky Basin was estimated to be 445 metric tons. This estimate was based on a weighted mean concentration from 160 samples collected during both high and low flows and the mean annual flow for the period of record. Since that time, phosphorus removal programs have resulted in a decrease in phosphorus loading from point sources of about 40 metric tons per year. During the period from 1975 to 1979, the annual phosphorus export averaged 420 metric tons per year and ranged from 257.5 to 563.4 metric tons (Table 4). The average deviation from the mean during this time was 74 metric tons. Should Bucyrus and Upper Sandusky meet the 1 mg/l effluent standard, an additional reduction in phosphorus inputs from point sources of 23 metric tons per year would be achieved. The total reduction program of 63 metric tons per year would still be less than the average deviation in annual loading observed during the past 5 years. Thus determining transmission coefficients of point source phosphorus by comparing known reductions of phosphorus inputs with observed reductions in phosphorus outputs is not feasible within the Sandusky Basin.

A second approach to determining transmission coefficients is to evaluate phosphorus/sediment ratios in basins with and without point sources. If all of the point source-derived phosphorus is delivered through the stream system, then subtracting the point source phosphorus inputs from the total phosphorus output should give nonpoint phosphorus/sediment ratios characteristic of strictly agricultural watersheds. This assumes that all of the observed sediment transport is derived from nonpoint sources. The data in Table 5 illustrates the application of this method. The mean annual yields, to which the method has been applied, were derived from the use of a minimum of three years of record at each station. A combination of weighted mean concentrations and long term flow duration tables were used to calculate the mean annual yields of sediments and total phosphorus (Baker, 1980).

The phosphorus/sediment ratios for the Broken Sword, Tymochtee and Wolf East watersheds reflect the ratios for agricultural watersheds lacking

source inputs. In the case of Bucyrus, the phosphorus sediment ratio (3.42) is much higher than the adjacent agricultural watershed (Broken Sword). Assuming 100% transmission of upstream point source inputs, these inputs are subtracted from the total phosphorus yield to give a nonpoint phosphorus yield. The resulting nonpoint phosphorus/sediment ratio (1.28) is much lower than the adjacent agricultural watershed. It should be noted that agricultural land use dominates all of these watersheds including those with point source inputs. The low calculated ratio suggests that not all of the point source inputs are resuspended and exported from the stream system.

Table 4. Annual variability in sediment and nutrient loading from the Sandusky River near Fremont, Ohio

Water Year	Discharge 10^9 M^3	Susp. Solids M. tons (mg/l)	Total Phosphorus M. tons (mg/l)	Sol. Reac. Phosphorus M. tons (mg/l)	Nitrate Nitrogen M. tons (mg/l)
1975	1.030	302,200 293	418.9 .406	72.42 .070	4709. 4.57
1976	.772	124,000 161	398.9 .517	49.67 .064	2621 3.39
1977	.629	98,800 157	257.5 .409	65.76 .104	3135 4.98
1978	1.391	193,500 139	463.4 .333	116.90 .084	4958 3.56
1979	1.087	285,500 262	563.4 .518	112.2 .103	5615 5.16

Table 5. Use of Phosphorus/Sediment Ratios to Analyze Delivery of Upstream Point Source Phosphorus Inputs

Location	Component	Mean Annual Sediment Yield M.T./yr.	Mean Annual Phosphorus Yield M.T./yr.	TP/SS g/kg
Bucyrus	Total	12,400	42.5	3.42
	Point Source		-26.6	
	"Nonpoint Source"		15.9	1.28
Upper Sandusky	Total	48,600	111.9	2.30
	Point Source		-32.5	
	"Nonpoint Source"		79.4	1.63
Broken Sword		18,900	31.0	1.64
Tymochtee		30,800	62.8	2.04
Wolf, East		12,900	29.8	2.31

The application of this method at Upper Sandusky gives less clear-cut results. The calculated nonpoint phosphorus/sediment ratio of 1.63 is lower than two of the agricultural watersheds but is about the same as the ratio in the Broken Sword Watershed. The relatively low ratios of point to nonpoint source phosphorus in these watersheds makes this approach to determining point source transmission characteristics difficult.

A third approach to evaluating the transmission of upstream point source phosphorus through the stream system would be to analyze the delivery of sediment through the system. One of the probable temporary sinks of phosphorus in the stream systems is through adsorption to sediments. Some fraction of these sediments will be deposited on flood plains during the large floods which account for much of the sediment and phosphorus yields. Point source-derived phosphorus which becomes adsorbed to these sediments could, therefore, be deposited on flood plains. The accumulation of materials on flood plains represents permanent sinks for sediment and phosphorus relative to the time-frames of water quality management planning. According to soil surveys in the Sandusky Basin, there are a number of flood plains upon which sediments are accumulating (Steiger, 1975). Quantification of this accumulation is lacking and consequently the extent of transmission losses of sediment and particulate phosphorus through deposition on flood plains cannot be readily estimated. Impoundments along streams and rivers could also provide permanent sinks for point source-derived phosphorus that is adsorbed on sediment particles.

Although it is probable that the transmission of point source-derived phosphorus through the stream system is less than 100%, quantitative determinations of transmission coefficient in large agricultural river basins is very difficult to attain.

Bioavailability: The instream deposition of phosphorus from upstream point sources could involve biological uptake by periphyton or rooted aquatic plants, adsorption to sediment particles or some type of chemical precipitation reaction. Storm routing methods which show resuspension of total phosphorus do not show release of soluble reactive phosphorus back into the water column (Melfi, et al. 1979). That portion of the deposited phosphorus that is delivered to Lake Erie apparently arrives as particulate phosphorus. It is probable that during its period of storage in the stream bed, at least some of the point source-derived phosphorus is converted to unavailable or slowly available particulate phosphorus. Part of it could be converted into refractory forms by biological processes while part could undergo chemical transformations. Once in the lake particulate phosphorus, whether bioavailable or not, is subject to removal from the water column through sedimentation. This particulate phosphorus is less available than soluble reactive phosphorus derived from nonpoint sources and delivered to the lake during storms or soluble reactive phosphorus delivered to the lake by direct point sources.

By far the highest loading rates of soluble reactive phosphorus to the lake occur during storm events. In the Sandusky Basin 50% of the annual export of soluble reactive phosphorus occurs during the 5% of the time with the highest fluxes. At these times, the orthophosphorus loading

rates exceeded 61.2 kg/hr. These rates dwarf not only the upstream point source inputs, but also the direct point sources in the basin, including Fremont at 0.85 kg/hr. and Sandusky at 1.5 kg/hr. (IJC, 1979). The higher flow velocities during these storm events probably result in a high delivery of this nonpoint-derived soluble reactive phosphorus through the estuarine and nearshore processing zones to the open lake system. It is possible that during non-storm conditions, soluble reactive phosphorus from direct municipal discharges is processed and deposited in the estuaries and nearshore zones in a fashion similar to the deposition of upstream point source phosphorus. Nearshore processing of phosphorus has been reported by Richards (1979). If estuarine and nearshore processing of direct point sources to the lake is extensive, then a mass balance of soluble reactive phosphorus to the open lake water could be dominated by soluble reactive phosphorus derived from nonpoint sources and delivered to the lake during storm events.

Since upstream point source-derived phosphorus is in a particulate form when it reaches the lake, it will be less available than phosphorus entering the lake from direct point sources. Soluble reactive phosphorus derived from nonpoint sources could be an extremely important component of the bioavailable phosphorus reaching the open lake system.

Ambient Stream Water Quality Effects

One effect of upstream point source phosphorus control programs is to lower the phosphorus concentration in the stream system, especially in the zones immediately downstream from outfalls. The effect of point source loading on stream phosphorus levels is greatest during periods of low stream flow. As stream flows increase, the increasing dilution of the point source effluents decreases the impact of the effluent on stream concentrations. Water quality problems could be associated with the elevated phosphorus concentrations if they result in increased growth of rooted aquatic plants, periphyton or phytoplankton. If these growths reach nuisance levels and cause excessive diurnal oxygen fluctuations, then ambient stream water quality problems could be attributed to the point source phosphorus inputs.

In the Sandusky Basin rooted aquatic plants are uncommon. Phytoplankton chlorophyll levels along the river were not decreased by the implementation of phosphorus removal programs along the river (unpublished data, Heidelberg Water Quality Laboratory). Nuisance growth of algae do develop along the river but these seem to be more related to periods of low stream flow and stream gradients than to phosphorus levels. Much of the time turbidity associated with the transport of fine clay probably limits growth of plant communities. It does not appear that the elevated phosphorus concentrations from point sources, where and when they occur in the Sandusky Basin, cause significant water quality problems.

There is a lack of information on the effects of nutrients on plant growth in stream systems. Responses probably vary considerably from stream to stream as well as with position in the stream system (Cummins, 1975). The need for additional studies on this topic for streams in southern Ontario has been recently cited (Wong, et al. 1979). In the river quality assessment program conducted for the Willamette River Basin in Oregon, it was concluded that flow augmentation was a more effective and economical

procedure for controlling algae than advanced waste treatment. (Rickert, et al., 1977).

Discussion

Although the data available in the Sandusky Basin does not currently provide quantitative values on the transmission coefficient of upstream point source phosphorus to Lake Erie or its bioavailability upon reaching the lake, it is clear that its form and mode of delivery to the lake is quite different than for direct point sources. The bulk of the upstream point source-derived phosphorus that does reach the lake will be delivered during storm events at which time it is a small part of the total particulate phosphorus load. The nonpoint component of the particulate phosphorus load is so variable that reductions in point source loads cannot be readily detected.

Because of in-stream processing of upstream point source phosphorus, the impacts of this phosphorus on lake water quality are likely to be quite different than for direct discharges to the lake. Consequently, different requirements for phosphorus removal should be considered for upstream point sources. This could include careful analyses of the costs for varying degrees of phosphorus removal at these plants. Consideration of the water quality benefits that could be achieved through diverting portions of funds needed to operate phosphorus removal programs to supporting nonpoint source implementation programs or flow augmentation programs should be considered.

Table 6. Summary of Municipal Point Source Phosphorus Loading to the Great Lakes, 1978^a

Basin	Direct Kg/day	Indirect Kg/day	Total Kg/day
Superior	351	291	641
Michigan	1,353	2,249	3,602
Huron	463	693	1,156
Erie	12,165	3,860	16,025
Ontario	5,240	1,644	6,884
Total	19,572 (69%)	8,737 (31%)	28,308
Detroit	7,178		
	12,394 (59%)	8,737 (41%)	

^a Source IJC, July, 1979.

Within the Great Lakes System, indirect point sources account for a considerable portion of the total point source phosphorus inputs (Table 6). More information is needed on the open lake impacts of phosphorus derived from upstream point sources in comparison with the impacts of soluble reactive phosphorus delivered during storm events. Lacking this information, the effectiveness of alternative control programs for the lakes cannot be accurately predicted.

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